

Integrating "CONNECT" science actions into biology lessons of secondary school classes

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Abstract

The purpose of this article is to present two examples of the implementation of CONNECT scientific actions, in biology lessons, to secondary school students, respecting the school curriculum.

CONNECT activities provides innovative, participatory teaching approaches based on the active involvement of students and their families, which can stimulate their interest in science and technology and, why not, the desire to pursue a scientific career.

As a secondary school biology teacher, I implemented the scientific actions "Renaturalization" and "Carbon Neutral", in the fifth grade and eighth grades, as an integral part of the biology lessons, respecting the school curriculum.

The activities corresponding to the scientific action "Renaturalization" were integrated in the fifth grade in the lessons belonging to the learning unit "Living things from the near and more distant environment - relationships between living things, the importance of living things for nature and human".

The activities corresponding to the "Carbon Neutral" scientific action were integrated in the eighth grade in the lessons belonging to the "Human and environmental health" learning unit.

The students were very interested in the debated topics, learned new investigative skills, learned to solve problems "step by step", showed creativity, responsibility and maturity in decision-making, acquired the ability to analyze the consequences of the decisions made. They worked as a team, tried to convince their families that the actions proposed by them are the best solutions for solving the discussed problems.

The benefits of implementing CONNECT can be summed up in three words: knowledge, skills, attitudes.

Keywords: scientific actions, renaturalization, neutral carbon, secondary school students, school curriculum

The concept of "Open schools for Open Societies" is an educational concept that revolutionizes education systems and is applied more and more in schools in Romania. It involves the active involvement in the educational processes of students, teachers, parents, specialists in the field but also of the local community, thus contributing to the development of society as a whole. If we compare modern and traditional education, we can say that the main difference is that modern education promotes a formative education, focused on the individual particularities of students, on their needs and interests, the teaching staff acting as a facilitator

of learning, while, traditional education promotes an informative education that is focused on the activity of the teacher, this being the source of information and having a dominant role.

The traditional education system focuses on explanatory-receptive-reproductive learning, while the modern education system is based on active-participatory learning, the student being constantly looking for new information, in his field of interest. Teaching science by integrating „ scientific action " as a complement to the activities of the school curriculum, facilitates the development of basic skills in science and technology in schools in Europe, European-recognized competences (European Commission / ECEA / Eurydice, 2012).

The CONNECT PROJECT is funded by the European Commission (2020-2023) under the grant agreement no. 872814. CONNECT activities offer innovative, participatory teaching approaches based on the active involvement of students and their families, which can stimulate their interest in science and technology and, why not, the desire to pursue a scientific career.

CONNECT scientific actions propose didactic scenarios based on the following three stages: CARE , KNOW 1, KNOW 2 , DO. They can be introduced by science teachers in lessons and can be adapted to the level of knowledge and understanding of students.

The concept of CARE, requires the science teacher, to stimulate students' interest in the topic approached, so that students become motivated, "to care" and of course to understand the scientific concepts they will use during their activities.

KNOW1 is an approach that allows the application of knowledge acquired in new contexts.

KNOW2 develops in students the skills needed to analyze the existing evidence in support of statements

DO involves evaluating the performance of students by coordinating the knowledge and skills acquired by them in the scientific field.

As a biology teacher at the gymnasium, in the period 2020-2023, we implemented the scientific actions „Renaturalization" and „Carbon Neutral", in the 5th and 8th grades, as an integral part of biology lessons, respecting the school curriculum .

The scientific action "Renaturalization" is designed to be integrated into the topic of interdependence between species. Thus, we integrated the activities "Renaturalization" in the biology lessons belonging to the learning unit "Living things from the near and more distant environment - relationships between living things, the importance of living things for nature and human" in the 5th grade (students aged 10-11 years).

The activities took place after the scenario CARE, KNOW, DO.

1. Initial testing of students' knowledge;
2. Wolf renaturalization in the UK: Student motivation; Understanding the scientific context; Applying knowledge about trophic relationships in a new context;
3. It's your turn: Solving similar problems, independently (Imagine the renaturalization of these animals in Romania: bison, laughter, bear. What effect would the renaturalization of each have on the ecosystem? Explain which animal would have the most positive effects on the ecosystem).

4. Renaturalization campaign: Students launched a campaign to persuade the public - pupils, teachers, parents, the local community, that the animal they choose must be renaturalized. To make the presentations they used in the campaign, they collected and evaluated evidence, selected the most convincing statement using logical reasoning.

Photo 1

Photo 2

The activities corresponding to the scientific action „ Neutral Carbon ”, we integrated them in the gymnasium biology program, in the lessons belonging to the learning unit „ Human and environmental health”, in the eighth grade (students aged 13-14 years). The scientific action "Neutral Carbon" uses 2 key concepts: the Earth's atmosphere and global warming.

I followed the didactic scenario recommended by CONNECT, with the following learning activities:

- 1.Challenge: Students researched the notions of neutral carbon and carbon footprint. They calculated the carbon footprint of their household.
- 2.Carbon: Students found out how companies generate CO2 emissions and applied the information they gained to help a cafe find out how to produce CO2 emissions.
3. Game: Students have evaluated the actions that the cafe can take to reduce its carbon footprint.
- 4.Recommendations: Students drafted a plan that included their recommendations for the cafe so that it becomes carbon neutral.

Photo 3

Photo 4

The students were very interested in the debated topics, learned new investigative skills, learned to solve problems "step by step", showed creativity, responsibility and maturity in decision-making, acquired the ability to analyze the consequences of the decisions made.

They worked as a team, tried to convince their families that the actions proposed by them are the best solutions for solving the discussed problems.

The benefits of implementing CONNECT can be summed up in three words: knowledge, skills, attitudes.

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